

RESEARCH REGARDING TELEWORK AND ITS IMPACT ON THE EMPLOYEE AND THE ORGANIZATION

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Abstract

Purpose – *The paper aims to present arguments for considering telework as a support process for sustainable business globalization.*

Methodology/approach – *A questionnaire-based research study was conducted on a sample of 268 Romanian people between 4 - 29 May 2020, in order to identify some aspects regarding respondents' opinion on telework and its impact on the employee and the organization.*

Findings – *Hypotheses regarding telework comparison to work performed at the employer's premises and changes occurred in the relationship with the organization were tested using SPSS. Our main results show that more than 50% of the respondents consider the changes involved by working remotely as being positive.*

Research limitations/implications – *The research was non-random, based on both judgment and accessibility, the results being valid at the sample level.*

Practical implications – *The main conclusion shows a positive perception of the respondents regarding telework impact. Employees may accept to work remotely, and this form of work organization can be considered in some fields of activity as a solution for business continuity in case of crisis.*

Originality/value – *The paper gives arguments for including the telework risk analysis among the company's processes risk analysis. The organizations' management must be prepared to manage telework implementation and to consider it as a part of Business Continuity Plan.*

Key words: *questionnaire, human resources, business continuity plan.*

Introduction

Globalization, as the process of interaction and integration among employees and companies worldwide, has grown because of communication technology and new technologies development. As a result, more employees were able to work from home or remote locations, using online networking for communication and work.

In the context of the European Employment Strategy, the European Framework Agreement on Telework was negotiated and signed in 2002 (EurWORK, 2010). Since then, many countries including Romania have developed the legislative aspects regarding telework and acted in the direction of increasing the number of employees working remotely. As far as Romania is concerned, the Parliament issued the "Law regarding the regulation of the telework activity" in 2018. According to it, the definition of telework emphasizes a few mandatory aspects of this form of work organization, related to: frequency and initiative (regularly and willingly), location (other than the one organized by the employer), the responsibilities of the employees working remotely (it fulfills the responsibilities specific to its position, occupation or job), repetitiveness (at least once a month) and the mandatory condition of using technology (using information and communication technology). (The Romanian parliament, 2018)

Telework was used to a small extent in Romania before March 2020 and few studies of its impact on the employee and the organization have been performed. A report regarding the use of telework in European Union (EurWORK, 2010) shows less than 3% level of telework in Romania. However, since

the beginning of the current COVID-19 sanitary crisis, this way of working has been and is used more and more in many fields of activity.

Research problem

Regarding the advantages and disadvantages of telework, there have been very few studies performed. Gajendran and Harrison (2007) performed “a meta-analysis of 46 studies in natural settings involving 12883 employees” and concluded that “telecommuting is likely better than bad for individuals”. The authors mention among the positive effects and telework advantages: “perceived autonomy, work–family conflict, job satisfaction, performance, turnover intent, and stress”, pointing out that “telecommuting also has no straightforward, damaging effects on the quality of workplace relationships or perceived career prospects”. The disadvantage mentioned by the authors, regarding telework, refers to the relations between coworkers, which can be deteriorated.

Quoting a series of psychological research, Abrams (2019) mentions that both employees and organizations may have benefits from using telework: “when it’s done right, telework can improve employee productivity, creativity and morale”. The article also mentions the fact that leadership may want to avoid telework because employees are less monitored, and performance may decrease. This could be understandable, as Sava and Bacali (2013) mention: “performance "fever" has developed globally in recent times; from individual level to business entities, everybody seems to improve performance”.

New abilities are needed in the present context in order to work remotely and both employees and organizations must be prepared for changes. It is also necessary that all aspects related to the impact of telework on the employee and the organization be analyzed by the organizations’ leadership and management, so that the best decisions are taken regarding the use of telework, especially in crisis situations, such as the pandemics generated by COVID- 19.

Applied research

The applied research was carried out during a research project together with the economic environment supported by De KLAUSEN company. The project aimed to perform some theoretical and practical research related to the impact of the human capital – through behavior, through value generating work or through its opposite – on the organizational results. One of the project’s activities consisted of performing a telework (remote work) and influence of technology related survey. The research instrument used was the questionnaire.

The criteria established for estimating the value of the information obtained through research were accuracy (the extent to which the information obtained would correctly describe the reality) and availability (the extent to which information could be obtained). The two criteria were considered for the decision on the implementation of the applied research (the investigated population and the research period for conducting the study). Considering the period of the research and the conditions in the external environment drastically marked by the COVID-19 sanitary crisis, which imposed the partial or total cessation of business activity and the use of telework, it was decided to perform the research as it follows:

- the investigated population – employed persons from Romania, preferably with telework experience
- the period of the study – one month, including the last two weeks of the emergency state period, established to reduce the effects of the COVID-19 sanitary crisis (period in which regular work was drastically limited in Romania, by law) and the first two weeks of the alert state instituted in Romania as a continuation of the emergency state.

At the end, 363 respondents took part in the research. 268 out of them declared that they used telework (remote work) and they were asked to answer the questions from the questionnaire related to the theme of this paper. Their responses will be presented below.

All participants to the telework and its impact related study, presented in this paper, experienced teleworking as students (27%), managers or employees (63%). According to the participants' profile presented below, all participants have telework experience, about 70 percent of them haven't had experience in using telework before COVID-19 sanitary crisis, more than 65 percent are female (66.42%), and over half of them (52.99%) are between 20 and 35 years old (figure 1). The respondents were students (about 25%) and employees (64%) working in education – teachers (14%), IT industry (9,5%), manufacturing and other industries (14%), public administration and defense (5,5%) and other fields of activity. About 11% of respondents did not agree to provide data related to gender, age group and field of activity.

Figure 1. Participants' profile

Findings

The research presented in this paper was performed from a double perspective: (1) telework comparison to work performed at the employer's premises and (2) the changes brought by telework in the employee's relationship with the organization. Therefore, the following part of the paper is structured according to the double assessment that was performed, as it follows:

(1) The first part presents the results regarding telework comparison to work performed at the employer's premises. The participants had the opportunity to express their opinion on telework, as they were asked to fill out one question that contained five items, developed around various aspects of telework comparison to work performed at the employer's premises, such as: Work performance, Work efficiency, Physical fatigue, Mental fatigue and Commitment to the organization. The participants' opinion regarding these aspects were captured using five-point comparison scales, ranging from: 1 – 'much lower' to 5 – 'much higher'.

(2) The second part presents the results regarding the changes brought by telework in the employee's relationship with the organization. The participants had the opportunity to express their opinions, as they were asked to fill out one question that contained five items, developed around various aspects, such as: Work climate, Collaboration and acceptance of ideas, Problem solving and decision making, Work organization and Work appreciation. The participants' opinion regarding the five mentioned aspects were captured using five-point scales, ranging from 1 – 'very negative (unacceptable)' to 5 – 'very positive (acceptable)'.

The data collected through the research instrument were analyzed using SPSS and the main results are presented as it follows.

Part 1 – Telework comparison to work performed at the employer’s premises

The research hypotheses have been tested using the SPSS statistical analysis and the results are summarized in Table 1. The main conclusion shows that, according to the participants in the survey, physical fatigue is lower in the case of telework as compared to ordinary work, while the commitment towards the organization is generally the same. The study does not confirm, at a sample level, a negative impact of telework on the employee, through the increase of psychological stress or on the organization through lower performance and work rate. Teleworking may have a positive impact on the employee, by a lower physical stress and a neutral impact on the organization.

Table 1. Results regarding telework comparison to work performed at the employer’s premises

<p>H₀₁: More than 40% of the respondents consider that Performance and Efficiency are lower through telework, than through ordinary work. H₁₁: Not more than 40% of the respondents consider that Performance and Efficiency are lower through telework than through ordinary work. – It’s confirmed</p>											
Work performance					Work efficiency						
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	much lower	17	6.3	6.3	6.3	Valid	much lower	25	9.3	9.3	9.3
	lower	79	29.5	29.5	35.8		lower	82	30.6	30.6	39.9
	about the same	115	42.9	42.9	78.7		about the same	97	36.2	36.2	76.1
	higher	45	16.8	16.8	95.5		higher	50	18.7	18.7	94.8
	much higher	12	4.5	4.5	100.0		much higher	14	5.2	5.2	100.0
	Total	268	100.0	100.0			Total	268	100.0	100.0	
<p>H₀₂: Less than 50% of the respondents consider that Physical Fatigue is lower through telework than through ordinary work. H₁₂: At least 50% of the respondents consider that Physical Fatigue is lower through telework than through ordinary work. – It’s confirmed</p>											
Physical fatigue											
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent						
Valid	much lower	49	18.3	18.3	18.3						
	lower	107	39.9	39.9	58.2						
	about the same	69	25.7	25.7	84.0						
	higher	34	12.7	12.7	96.6						
	much higher	9	3.4	3.4	100.0						
	Total	268	100.0	100.0							
<p>H₀₃: More than 40% of the respondents consider that Mental Fatigue is greater through telework than through ordinary work.</p>											

H13: Not more than 40% of the respondents consider that Mental Fatigue is greater through telework than through ordinary work. – It's confirmed

Mental fatigue					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	much lower	37	13.8	13.8	13.8
	lower	64	23.9	23.9	37.7
	about the same	71	26.5	26.5	64.2
	higher	63	23.5	23.5	87.7
	much higher	33	12.3	12.3	100.0
Total		268	100.0	100.0	

H04: Less than 30% of the respondents consider that Commitment is higher through telework than through ordinary work.

H14: At least 30% of the respondents consider that Commitment is higher through telework than through ordinary work. – It's confirmed

Commitment					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	much lower	13	4.9	4.9	4.9
	lower	57	21.3	21.3	26.1
	about the same	116	43.3	43.3	69.4
	higher	64	23.9	23.9	93.3
	much higher	18	6.7	6.7	100.0
Total		268	100.0	100.0	

H05: Performance and Efficiency are generally lower through telework than through ordinary work. – It's denied

H06: Physical Fatigue is generally lower through telework than through ordinary work. – It's confirmed

H07: Mental Fatigue is generally higher through telework than through ordinary work. – It's denied

H08: Commitment is generally approximately the same through telework than through ordinary work. – It's confirmed

Descriptive Statistics				One-Sample Test					
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Test Value = 3					
				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Work performance	268	2.84	.934	-2.879	267	.004	-.164	-.28	-.05
Work efficiency	268	2.80	1.019	-3.238	267	.001	-.201	-.32	-.08
Physical fatigue	268	2.43	1.034	-9.036	267	.000	-.571	-.70	-.45
Mental fatigue	268	2.97	1.234	-.445	267	.656	-.034	-.18	.11
Commitment	268	3.06	.956	1.086	267	.278	.063	-.05	.18
Valid N (listwise)	268								

The superior and inferior limits of the confidence interval for testing the H05 - H08 hypotheses have been checked using the Explore option in SPSS. It can be seen that we can state with 95% confidence that:

- The averages obtained from the respondents' assesment regarding Performance and Efficiency are between 2,72 – 2,95 and respectively 2,68 – 2,92. In conclusion **H05 is denied**.

Descriptives				Descriptives			
		Statistic	Std. Error			Statistic	Std. Error
Work performance	Mean	2.84	.057	Work efficiency	Mean	2.80	.062
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.72		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.68
		Upper Bound	2.95			Upper Bound	2.92
	5% Trimmed Mean	2.82	5% Trimmed Mean		2.78		
	Median	3.00	Median		3.00		
	Variance	.872	Variance		1.038		
	Std. Deviation	.934	Std. Deviation		1.019		
	Minimum	1	Minimum		1		
	Maximum	5	Maximum		5		
	Range	4	Range		4		
	Interquartile Range	1	Interquartile Range		1		
	Skewness	.194	.149		Skewness	.177	.149
	Kurtosis	-.123	.297		Kurtosis	-.445	.297

- The averages obtained from the respondents' assesment regarding Physical Fatigue are between 2,30 – 2,55. In conclusion **H₀₆ is confirmed.**
- The averages obtained from the respondents' assesment regarding Mental Fatigue are between 2,82 – 3,18. In conclusion **H₀₇ is denied.**

Descriptives				Descriptives			
		Statistic	Std. Error			Statistic	Std. Error
Physical fatigue	Mean	2.43	.063	Mental fatigue	Mean	2.97	.075
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.30		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.82
		Upper Bound	2.55			Upper Bound	3.11
	5% Trimmed Mean	2.38	5% Trimmed Mean		2.96		
	Median	2.00	Median		3.00		
	Variance	1.070	Variance		1.523		
	Std. Deviation	1.034	Std. Deviation		1.234		
	Minimum	1	Minimum		1		
	Maximum	5	Maximum		5		
	Range	4	Range		4		
	Interquartile Range	1	Interquartile Range		2		
	Skewness	.498	.149		Skewness	.016	.149
	Kurtosis	-.305	.297		Kurtosis	-.978	.297

- The averages obtained from the respondents' assesment regarding Commitment are 2,95 – 3,18. In conclusion **H₀₈ is confirmed.**

Descriptives			
		Statistic	Std. Error
Commitment	Mean	3.06	.058
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.95
		Upper Bound	3.18
	5% Trimmed Mean	3.07	
	Median	3.00	
	Variance	.914	
	Std. Deviation	.956	
	Minimum	1	
	Maximum	5	
	Range	4	
	Interquartile Range	2	
	Skewness	.002	.149
	Kurtosis	-.230	.297

Part 2 – Changes brought by telework in the employee – organization relationship

The research hypotheses have been tested using the SPSS statistical analysis and the results are summerized in Table 2. The main conclusion shows that changes in the Work climate, Colaboration, Problem solving and decision making, Work organization and Work appreciation are perceived as positive ones when working remotely.

Table 2. Changes brought by telework in the employee – organization relationship

H₀₉: More than 50% of the respondents appreciate the changes related to Work climate, Problem solving, Work appreciation as being positive and acceptable when working remotely. – It's confirmed
 H₁₉: Not more than 50% of the respondents appreciate the changes related to Work climate, Problem solving, Work assesment as being positive and acceptable when working remotely.

Work climate

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid very negative (unacceptable)	2	.7	.7	.7
negative	21	7.8	7.8	8.6
neutral	94	35.1	35.1	43.7
pozitive	115	42.9	42.9	86.6
very positive (acceptable)	36	13.4	13.4	100.0
Total	268	100.0	100.0	

Problem solving and decision making

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid negative	26	9.7	9.7	9.7
neutral	86	32.1	32.1	41.8
pozitive	126	47.0	47.0	88.8
very positive (acceptable)	30	11.2	11.2	100.0
Total	268	100.0	100.0	

Work appreciation

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid very negative (unacceptable)	3	1.1	1.1	1.1
negative	30	11.2	11.2	12.3
neutral	94	35.1	35.1	47.4
pozitive	110	41.0	41.0	88.4
very positive (acceptable)	31	11.6	11.6	100.0
Total	268	100.0	100.0	

H₀₁₀: More than 60% of the respondents appreciate the changes related to Collaboration and Work organization as being positive and acceptable when working remotely. – It's confirmed
 H₁₁₀: Not more than 60% of the respondents appreciate the changes related to Collaboration and Work organization as being positive and acceptable when working remotely.

Collaboration

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid negative	27	10.1	10.1	10.1
neutral	71	26.5	26.5	36.6
pozitive	140	52.2	52.2	88.8
very positive (acceptable)	30	11.2	11.2	100.0
Total	268	100.0	100.0	

Work organization				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid very negative (unacceptable)	2	.7	.7	.7
negative	33	12.3	12.3	13.1
neutral	64	23.9	23.9	36.9
positive	127	47.4	47.4	84.3
very positive (acceptable)	42	15.7	15.7	100.0
Total	268	100.0	100.0	

H011: The changes related to Work climate, Collaboration, Problem solving and decision making, Work organization and Work appreciation are generally appreciated as being positive when working remotely.

One-Sample test was used to test the hypothesis. The inferior and superior limits of the confidence interval have been verified by using the Explore option in SPSS.

One-Sample Statistics					One-Sample Test					
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Test Value = 3					
					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Work climate	268	3.60	.844	.052	11.728	267	.000	.604	.50	.71
Collaboration	268	3.65	.810	.049	13.041	267	.000	.646	.55	.74
Problem solving and decision making	268	3.60	.813	.050	12.022	267	.000	.597	.50	.69
Work organization	268	3.65	.914	.056	11.629	267	.000	.649	.54	.76
Work appreciation	268	3.51	.880	.054	9.435	267	.000	.507	.40	.61

One-Sample Test						
	Test Value = 4					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Work climate	-7.674	267	.000	-.396	-.50	-.29
Collaboration	-7.161	267	.000	-.354	-.45	-.26
Problem solving and decision making	-8.115	267	.000	-.403	-.50	-.31
Work organization	-6.283	267	.000	-.351	-.46	-.24
Work appreciation	-9.158	267	.000	-.493	-.60	-.39

Descriptives			
	Statistic	Std. Error	
Work climate	Mean	3.60	.052
95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	3.50	
	Upper Bound	3.71	
5% Trimmed Mean	3.62		
Median	4.00		
Variance	.712		
Std. Deviation	.844		
Minimum	1		
Maximum	5		
Range	4		
Interquartile Range	1		
Skewness	-.238	.149	
Kurtosis	-.138	.297	

Descriptives			
	Statistic	Std. Error	
Collaboration	Mean	3.65	.049
95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	3.55	
	Upper Bound	3.74	
5% Trimmed Mean	3.66		
Median	4.00		
Variance	.657		
Std. Deviation	.810		
Minimum	2		
Maximum	5		
Range	3		
Interquartile Range	1		
Skewness	-.416	.149	
Kurtosis	-.249	.297	

Descriptives			
	Statistic	Std. Error	
Problem solving and decision making	Mean	3.60	.050
95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	3.50	
	Upper Bound	3.69	
5% Trimmed Mean	3.61		
Median	4.00		
Variance	.661		
Std. Deviation	.813		
Minimum	2		
Maximum	5		
Range	3		
Interquartile Range	1		
Skewness	-.232	.149	
Kurtosis	-.407	.297	

Descriptives			
	Statistic	Std. Error	
Work organization	Mean	3.65	.056
95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	3.54	
	Upper Bound	3.76	
5% Trimmed Mean	3.67		
Median	4.00		
Variance	.835		
Std. Deviation	.914		
Minimum	1		
Maximum	5		
Range	4		
Interquartile Range	1		
Skewness	-.463	.149	
Kurtosis	-.312	.297	

Descriptives

		Statistic	Std. Error	
Work appreciation	Mean	3.51	.054	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	3.40	
		Upper Bound	3.61	
	5% Trimmed Mean	3.52		
	Median	4.00		
	Variance	.775		
	Std. Deviation	.880		
	Minimum	1		
	Maximum	5		
	Range	4		
	Interquartile Range	1		
Skewness	-.255	.149		
Kurtosis	-.229	.297		

It can be seen that we can state with 95% confidence that the averages obtained from the respondents' assessment regarding changes in the previously mentioned aspects are between: 3,50 – 3,71 (work climate); 3,55 – 3,74 (collaboration); 3,50 – 3,69 (problem solving and decision making); 3,54 – 3,76 (work organization) and respectively 3,40 – 3,61 (work appreciation). In conclusion **H₀₁₁ is confirmed.**

Comparative analysis on telework assessment, by fields of activity

To perform the comparative analysis by fields of activity, the investigated sample was divided using the Select Cases option in SPSS, into layers represented by the field of activity. The average values for all the 10 investigated aspects related to telework have been calculated, for the fields of activity represented by a number of more than 25 respondents: education – student (65), education – teacher (38), IT industry (25) and other industries (30). Table 3 presents the results of the statistical analyses and Figure 2 a few observations regarding the identified differences.

Table 3. Comparative analysis on telework assessment by fields of activity

Statistics											
		Work performance	Work efficiency	Physical fatigue	Mental fatigue	Commitment	Work climate	Collaboration	Problem solving and decision making	Work organization	Work appreciation
N	Valid	268	268	268	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		2.84	2.80	2.43	2.97	3.06	3.60	3.65	3.60	3.65	3.51

Field of activity					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	unreported	30	11.2	11.2	11.2
	education - student	65	24.3	24.3	35.4
	education - teacher	38	14.2	14.2	49.6
	IT industry	25	9.3	9.3	59.0
	manufacturing	7	2.6	2.6	61.6
	other industries	30	11.2	11.2	72.8

IF Field of activity = Education – student

Statistics						Statistics					
		Work performance	Work efficiency	Physical fatigue	Mental fatigue	Commitment	Work climate	Collaboration	Problem solving and decision making	Work organization	Work appreciation
N	Valid	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		2.63	2.51	2.40	3.26	2.82	3.46	3.49	3.40	3.54	3.46
Skewness		.011	.129	.599	-.102	.234	-.043	-.556	.026	-.643	-.271
Std. Error of Skewness		.297	.297	.297	.297	.297	.297	.297	.297	.297	.297
Kurtosis		-.414	-.555	-.442	-1.318	-.562	-.498	-.389	-.308	.100	.189
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.586	.586	.586	.586	.586	.586	.586	.586	.586	.586

IF Field of activity = Education – teacher

Statistics						Statistics					
		Work performance	Work efficiency	Physical fatigue	Mental fatigue	Commitment	Work climate	Collaboration	Problem solving and decision making	Work organization	Work appreciation
N	Valid	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38	38
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		2.61	2.45	3.00	3.58	3.58	3.61	3.66	3.63	3.68	3.42
Skewness		-.159	.352	-.109	-.418	-.266	-.622	-.839	-.882	-.844	-.526
Std. Error of Skewness		.383	.383	.383	.383	.383	.383	.383	.383	.383	.383
Kurtosis		-.035	-.215	-.927	-.572	-.322	.267	.681	.455	.529	.110
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.750	.750	.750	.750	.750	.750	.750	.750	.750	.750

IF Field of activity = IT industry						IF Field of activity = other industries					
Statistics						Statistics					
	Work performance	Work efficiency	Physical fatigue	Mental fatigue	Commitment	Work climate	Collaboration	Problem solving and decision making	Work organization	Work appreciation	
N	Valid	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Mean		3.44	3.56	2.20	2.80	3.52	3.64	3.72	3.76	3.52	
Skewness		.199	-.015	.854	.193	-.667	-.942	-.461	-.312	-.667	
Std. Error of Skewness		.464	.464	.464	.464	.464	.464	.464	.464	.464	
Kurtosis		-.436	-.670	1.128	-.653	-.060	.857	.656	.312	-.060	
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.902	.902	.902	.902	.902	.902	.902	.902	.902	

Regarding telework comparison to work performed at the employer's premises:

- The group of investigated students and the group of investigated teachers consider work performance and work efficiency lower – below average (2,63 and 2,51 respectively – for students and 2,61 and 2,45 respectively – for teachers).
- The group of IT industry investigated respondents consider work performance and work efficiency as being higher – above average (3,44 and 3,56 respectively).
- The group of investigated teachers appreciate physical fatigue approximately the same –at an average (3).
- The group of investigated students and the group of investigated teachers consider mental fatigue higher – above average (3,26, 3,58 respectively)
- The group of IT industry and other industries investigated respondents consider mental fatigue a little lower– below average (2,80, 2,60 respectively).
- The group of investigated teachers consider the commitment towards the organization as being higher – above average (3,58).

Changes brought by telework in the employee – organization relationship

- The group of investigated teachers consider work appreciation approximately the same – a little above average (3,42).

Figure 2. Differences in the respondents' assesment of telework

Discussion and conclusions

The results of the study presented in this paper show that telework may have a positive impact on the employee by lowering the physical stress and a neutral impact on the organization. The study does not confirm, at a sample level, a negative impact of telework on the employee through higher physical stress or on the organization through lower work performance and efficiency.

According to the activity field, work performance and efficiency are seen differently when working remotely: a possible negative impact of telework can be identified in education through a lower work performance and work efficiency and a positive impact in IT. Taking into consideration the number of respondents in the previously mentioned fields and the fact that the sample was non-randomly chosen, there is further research necessary to be performed in order to confirm some activity field related conclusions.

The paper aimed to find arguments for considering telework as a support process for sustainable business globalization. Being a work process performed according to the conditions specified by the legislation in force, this form of work organization may be taken into consideration as a solution for business continuity, in particular areas of activity, in case of crisis, such as epidemics, pandemics, calamities, etc. For the situations that require financial investments such as alocation of funds or

auctions, besides respecting the ISO 9001:2015 and ISO 14001:2015 specifications, Romania also asks, more and more frequently, that organizations prove that they have a procedure for business continuity, according to ISO 22301:2019 specifications. According to the standard's requirements, the organization is obligated to evaluate business continuity risks, to establish and periodically test a Business Continuity Plan in order to provide a response to disturbances and possible resuming of activity as soon as possible.

As a conclusion, the organizations' management must be prepared to manage telework implementation and to consider it as a part of Business Continuity Plan. The paper gives arguments for neutral or positive impact of telework, for using this form of work organization and for including the telework risk analysis among the company's processes risk analysis.

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